

(IV).⁸ By reaction with zinc/ethanol⁴, (IV) led to 1-bromo-*p*-menth-4(8)-ene (V) and the latter was selectively dehydrobrominated to (I) using silver nitrate-dimethyl sulphoxide reagent⁵.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Pmr spectra are in carbon tetrachloride and ir spectra are from thin film. Glc was run on an SE-30 column.

1,8-Dibromo-*p*-menthane(III): d-Limonene was converted into (III) adopting Wallach's procedure;¹ m.p. and mixed m.p. 64°.

1,4,8-Tribromo-*p*-menthane(IV): A clear solution of the dibromoderivative (III) (20 g) in carbon tetrachloride (120 ml) was brominated under ultraviolet irradiation.² Evaporation of the solvent followed by crystallisation from ethyl acetate-methanol gave (IV) (18 g), m.p. 110°, (lit.² 109-110°); (Found: Br, 63.36 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₇Br₃: Br, 63.66 per cent).

1-Bromo-*p*-menth-4(8)-ene (V): To a vigorously stirred suspension of (IV) (14 g), in dry ether (70 ml) and absolute ethanol (14 ml) at 0-5°, zinc dust (2.42 g) was added and the stirring continued for 13 hr. (It was observed that excessive cooling resulted in slow and partial debromination). The resulting clear solution was washed with water till free of bromide ion and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of ether under suction followed by recrystallisation from methanol afforded (V) (5.53 g), m.p. 34°-35°, (lit.⁴ 34-35°); (Found: Br, 37.6 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₇Br: Br, 37.2 per cent); pmr: δ 1.65 (s, 6H, CH₃-C=C), 1.8 (s, 3H, CH₃-C-Br), 2.01 (m, 4H, -CH₂-C=C), 2.31 (m, 4H, -CH₂-C-Br); ir: 2960, 2920, 2862, 1630, 1440, 1370, 770 cm⁻¹.

1,4(8)-*p*-Menthadlene (I): The monobromide (V) (5.53 g) in dimethyl sulphoxide (23 ml) was stirred with a solution of silver nitrate (4.33 g) in dimethyl sulphoxide (20 ml) at ~30° for 2 hr. The precipitated silver chloride was removed by filtration, washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°)(15 ml) and the filtrate extracted with petroleum ether (10×5 ml), washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent stripped by evaporation. Vacuum distillation of the oil received yielded homogeneous terpinolene (1.8 g); glc: single peak; b.p. 120°-121°/100 mm; n_D²⁰ 1.4861; (Found: C, 88.49; H, 11.51 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₆: C, 88.16; H,

11.84 per cent); pmr: δ 1.6 (broad, 9H, CH₃-C=C), 1.9 (m, 2H, -CH₂-C=C), 2.2 (m, 2H, -CH₂-C=) 2.6 (m, 2H, =C-CH₂-C=) and 5.25 (m, 1H, -CH=C); ir: 2960, 2920, 2862, 1630, 1440, 1370, 790 cm⁻¹; tetrabromide m.p. and mixed m.p. 116°.

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Stability Constants of Complexes of 2-Hydroxy-5-nitropropiophenoneoxime with Ni(II), Co(II) Zn(II) and Mn(II)

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THIS communication reports the investigations of stability constants of complexes of 2-hydroxy-5-nitropropiophenoneoxime with Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Mn(II) by Calvin-Bjerrum technique as applied by Irving and Rossotti¹ at 40° ($\mu \approx 0.1M$ NaClO₄) in water-dioxane (25 : 75 v/v) medium.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-5-nitropropiophenoneoxime was prepared by the aqueous ethanolic alkali method from ketone. Its stock solution was prepared by dissolving the required amount in purified dioxane² (S. Merck technical grade). All solutions and pH-measurements were made as described earlier³.

Three titrations, viz. titration of (i) free perchloric acid, (ii) free perchloric acid plus the reagent and (iii) free acid plus the reagent plus the metal ion, were done against standard NaOH.

Results and Discussion

It was observed that \bar{n}_H values did not fall in to the range 0 to 1, indicating that either the hydrogen of oximino group did not dissociate or its dissociation overlapped the dissociation of phenolic hydrogen. Assuming the later possibility an attempt was made to evaluate the two constants ${}^pK^{H_1}$ and K^{H_2} by the method of least squares⁴. It gives a negative value for the product of ${}^pK^{H_1} \cdot {}^pK^{H_2}$, however ${}^pK^{H_2}$ is positive. Therefore, it was concluded that only the phenolic-OH is dissociated. Thus 2-hydroxy-5-nitropropiophenoneoxime was considered monobasic and the \bar{n}_H values accordingly were reduced by 1. The practical proton-ligand stability constant, $\log {}^pK^H$, has been obtained as the Bjerrum half-integral value. The same has also been calculated at different points using the equation

$$\log {}^pK^{H=B} + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1 - \bar{n}_H}$$

The average value of $\log {}^pK^H$ (9.20) obtained by the pointwise calculation is in good agreement with the half-integral value (Table 1).

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BIVALENT COMPLEXES WITH 2-HYDROXY-5-NITROPROPIOPHENONEOXIME

Metal	Method		
	Half-integral	Least squares	
H(II)	—	-18.88	$\log P_{K_1}^H \cdot \log P_{K_2}^H$
	—	-10.02	$\log P_{K_1}^H$
	9.21	8.86	$\log P_{K_2}^H$
Ni(II)	11.74	11.74	$\log \beta_2$
	6.17	5.64	$\log K_1$
	5.57	6.10	$\log K_2$
Co(II)	13.95	14.03	$\log \beta_2$
	8.66	8.71	$\log K_1$
	5.29	5.32	$\log K_2$
Zn(II)	8.87	8.89	$\log \beta_2$
	4.72	4.17	$\log K_1$
	4.15	4.72	$\log K_2$
Mn(II)	8.98	8.99	$\log \beta_2$
	5.31	5.38	$\log K_1$
	3.67	3.61	$\log K_2$

In all the systems the highest values of \bar{n} are more than 1 (Fig. 1), indicating that 1:1 and 1:2 complexes are formed. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were calculated by the methods of half-integral and least squares (Table 1). The results given in Table 1, show that the order of stability is Zn < Co > Ni > Mn. It can be seen that the order is in agreement with Irving-Williams order⁵.

Fig. 1. Formation curves of bivalent metal complexes with 2-hydroxy-5-nitropropiophenoneoxime.

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Reactions of Boric Acid with Chelating Ligands in Acetic Anhydride

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IN continuation of our work on the chemistry of borates¹⁻³, we have undertaken a scheme to study in details the reactions of boric acid with various Lewis bases in different media. A recent report on the preparation of diacetatopropenyleniumdioxaborates⁴ prompted us to report our results on the preparation of chelates of boroacetate with monobasic bidentate oxygen-donor ligands. The boroacetate complex of 1-hydroxyanthraquinone has been reported many years ago⁵.

Experimental

Chemicals and solvents were purified and dried by standard methods. U. V. spectra were recorded in CH_2Cl_2 solution using Beckman Du-2 spectrophotometer. I. R. spectra were recorded in nujol mull or hexachlorobutadiene. The analyses of C and H were done by the Microanalyst of C. D. R. I., Lucknow. Dr. Alfred Bernhardt's Microanalytical Laboratory, Germany.

Preparation of the chelates of boroacetate: The following general method was used for the preparation of boroacetate chelates and all the reactions were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere.

Boric acid (0.05 mole) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (40-50 ml) by gently refluxing. The resulting solution of diborontetraacetate was cooled to 10° and the chelating ligands (e. g. acetylacetone, salicylaldehyde, orthohydroxyacetophenone, and acetoacetone) (0.05 mol) was added. The solid compounds isolated were recrystallised from acetic anhydride or dry acetone, and stored in vacuum desiccator or in vacuum-sealed ampoules to prevent hydrolysis.

(*acac*) $B(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ (I): White; m. p. 180°-181°; Found: C, 47.00; H, 6.21%; λ_{max} (nm) 295 (log ϵ = 4.30); Calc. for (I): C, 47.41; H, 5.70%.

(*sal*) $B(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ (II): White; m. p. 198°-200°; Found: C, 53.28; H, 4.60%; λ_{max} (nm) 315 (log ϵ = 4.41); Calc. for (II): C, 52.84; H, 4.40%.

(*hap*) $B(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ (III): Pale yellow; m. p. 200°-202°; Found: C, 53.28; H, 5.45%; λ_{max} (nm) 305 (log ϵ = 4.38); Calc. for (III): C, 54.59; H, 4.92%.

(*aact*) $B(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ (IV): Pale yellow; m. p. 245°-250°; Found: C, 54.72; H, 4.95%; Calc. for (IV): C, 55.12; H, 5.25%.

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